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2012 i-CREATE

24th - 26th JULY, ITE College East, Singapore

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24th - 26th JULY, Singapore

International Convention on Rehabilitation Engineering & Assistive Technology

Venue sponsor:
Institute of Technical Education

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i-CREATE²⁰¹²

international Convention on Rehabilitation Engineering & Assistive Technology

24 - 26 July 2012
ITE College East, Singapore

Jointly Organized by:

The Singapore Therapeutic, Assistive &
Rehabilitative Technologies (START) Centre

The Thailand's National Electronics and Computer
Technology Center (NECTEC)

CONTENTS

Welcome	1
General Information	2
Paper Session Information	3
Poster Session Information	4
Site Visit	5
Plenary Sessions	6
Workshop Sessions	10
Forum Sessions	17
Program Overview	19
Paper Presentations	25
Student Design Challenge	39
Authors Index	42

Welcome

Welcome to *i-CREAtE*, the International Convention on Rehabilitation Engineering and Assistive Technology 2012. The theme this year's annual conference is "Assistive Technology in an Inclusive Community"

There are 4 exciting Plenary Speakers, 12 workshops, 3 forums and more than 80 papers and posters for you to share technical exchanges between advocates and professionals from across the world attending *i-CREAtE*. We are confident that *i-CREAtE* 2012 will be an exciting platform to share ideas and best practices in the disabilities fields and exchange information on advanced technologies, equipment, techniques and materials applied in the field of Assistive & Rehabilitative Technology.

We are very honored to have the presence of **Her Royal Highness Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn and Acting Minister of Community Development, Youth & Sports Singapore** to gracing the opening of the convention.

Enjoy the brain stimulating sessions, be active at the workshops, get involved in the forums and most importantly network with fellow professionals. Over lunch, tea breaks and at the Gala Dinner, share your view and suggestions as they are also interested in improving the lives of people with disability for them to enjoy living in an inclusive community independently.

We wish you a pleasant time at *i-CREAtE* 2012.

Prof Pairash THAJCHAYAPONG
& Prof ANG Wei Tech
General Chair

General Information

Conference Date:	24 - 26 July 2012 (Tue,Wed,Thu) ITE College East
Conference Venue:	10 Simei Avenue, Singapore 486047
Opening Hours:	08:00hr to 17:00hr daily
Admission:	Open to registered delegates only.
Registration:	Admin Block, Level 3 Foyer
Plenary Sessions & SDC Award Ceremony	Admin Block, Level 3 Auditorium
Workshops & Paper Presentations:	Business Block Level 3 Room B03-13, B03-14, B03-15/16, B03-17
SDC Presentations	Function Hall, Level 3 (Design) Room B03-15/16 (Technology)
SDC Exhibit / Poster & Exhibition Lunch and Tea Break:	Function Hall, Level 3 Admin Block, Level 3 Foyer
Gala Dinner *hawker fare nite	25 July 2012 (19:00hr – 21:00hr) Atrium, Admin Block Level 1 <i>*open to FULL pass delegates & SDC students</i>
Secretariat Room	Admin Block, Level 3 Beside Function Hall

Paper Session Information

All Chairpersons and Speakers are requested to be in their respective session rooms at least 10 minutes prior to the commencement of each session. A total of 15 minutes has been allocated for each oral presentation, including time for questions (12 minutes presentation + 3 minutes question and answer.) Session chairpersons will strictly enforce this limit. Presenters are requested to keep their presentations within the time limits stated. Presentations must be carried out using **Microsoft PowerPoint**. No OHP or slide projector will be provided.

For presenters using Microsoft PowerPoint, they are encouraged to bring their files on a USB flash drive (thumb drive) and upload their files at the Secretariat Room on the allocated time below:

24 July 2012

08:30 to 09:30hr / 12:30-13:30hr / 15:00-15:30hr

25 & 26 July 2012

08:30 to 09:30hr / 10:30 to 11:00hr / 12:00-13:00hr

Presenters may also use their own laptops if their presentations require special software or codec but please inform the Conference Secretariat in by 24 July 2012 of the arrangement.

Poster Session Information

All poster presenters are given 2 minutes airtime at the allocated paper session on 25/26 July 2012 (see paper presentation sessions for details) and 30 minutes presentation time on 25 July 2012 at the Function Hall.

Guidelines for poster presentations

Poster must be presented in A1 poster format at the conference in paper, vinyl or fabric poster of A1 size (594mm x 841mm).

Poster presenters will be provided with a vertical display panel with pins– approx. 1800 x 1200mm

The set up time is on 24 July 2012 (Tue) 09:00hr – 12:30hr and should be packed down on 26 July 2012 (Thu) by 16:00hr.

Presenters are required to attend their poster session on 25 July 2012 from 13:00hr – 13:30hr.

Site Visit (Day ONE – 24 July 2012, Tue)

Duration - 09:00hr – 12:30hr (4.5hrs)

Site Visit A

09:15hr – 10:15hr

ITE College East

Contact: Mr Chong Chon Hsien, Course Manager

Tel: (65) 6544 9490

10:45hr – 11:45hr

Society for the Physically Disabled

Contact: Miss Sarah Yong, Clinical Head

Tel: (65) 6579 0730

Site Visit B

09:15hr – 10:30hr

Spastic Children Association of Singapore

Contact: Mr D. Senthil Kumar, Senior Physiotherapist

Tel: (65) 6585 5627

11:00hr – 12:00hr

Centre for Advanced Rehabilitation Therapeutics (CART) @
Tan Tock Seng Hospital

All delegates are to register for either one site visit at the Registration Counter (Admin Block level 3 Foyer) on 24 July 2012, from 08:00hr – 08:45hr. The tour buses will leave at 09:00hr and back to ITE College East by 12:30hr for lunch.

Plenary Sessions

Day TWO – 25 July 2012 (Wed)

Prof. Dr. Roger Gassert

Assistant Professor

Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule-
Zürich (ETH-Zürich), Switzerland

Venue: Auditorium

Time: 13:30hr – 14:10hr

Feel to Move: Assessment, Restoration and Augmentation of Hand Sensorimotor Function

Despite intensive therapy, sensorimotor recovery after neurological injury is often incomplete, restricting patients in their activities of daily living. The efficacy of therapeutic interventions and assistive technology is limited by our understanding of the neural mechanisms underlying sensorimotor control, and how physical therapy and novel technologies can optimally engage neuroplasticity and promote recovery. In order to minimize the disability, objective and sensitive assessments and patient-tailored rehabilitation therapies and assistive technologies are required. However, current rehabilitation approaches focus mostly on motor aspects, while there is increasing evidence that recovery of motor function may be impeded by sensory deficits. To address this limitation, we use a multidisciplinary approach combining robotics, haptics, virtual reality, psychophysics, neuroscience and user/clinical studies, in order to develop novel tools to assess, restore and augment sensory and thereby motor function in therapy and long-term assistance.

Mr Marcus King
Distinguished Scientist
Research leader : Assistive Devices
Industrial Research Limited, New Zealand

Venue: Auditorium

Time: 14:15hr – 14:55hr

Upper limb rehabilitation using virtual reality for stroke survivors

Stroke is the greatest cause of adult disability in the world with hemiparesis being a common outcome. Upper limb rehabilitation remains problematic post stroke; whereas 83% of stroke survivors learn to walk again, only 5 to 20% attain complete recovery of their affected upper limbs. There is a need for effective upper limb rehabilitation tools that provide large repetitions of functional movements for use at home without constant therapist supervision. Robot-assisted physiotherapy can alleviate therapist work load by providing autonomous training, but the cost to benefit ratio and effectiveness needs to improve. Virtual reality, provided via computer games, allows the user to interact with a simulated environment, providing engaging and motivating practise of upper limb movements through manipulation of the interface device. This offers new clinical assessment and rehabilitation options. This presentation will discuss the future of this field and the opportunities of homecare rehabilitation for stroke survivors.

Mrs Desleigh de Jonge
Associate Lecturer
University of Queensland, Australia
Member of Editorial Board for Disability and Rehabilitation : Assistive Technology for Informa Healthcare

Venue: Auditorium

Time: 17:15hr – 17:45hr

The Art and Science of Choosing and Using Technology

There is an abundance of technologies on the market. Devices come and go but only a select few capture the market. Consequently, there is a growing mound of disused devices that, for one or other reason, haven't quite met our needs. Although there may be a technology for every purpose, a number of questions remain. How do we determine the best technologies for our needs and how do we ensure we get the most out of the technologies we purchase? More importantly, how do people with disabilities identify the right technology from the overwhelming range of options available and how do we ensure the technology remains useful to them? This presentation examines the role and impact of 'soft' technologies in the successful selection and effective use of 'hard' technologies ensuring that the art of identifying and using technology works in harmony with the science employed to design and operate it.

Ms Judy Wee
Access Consultant and Founder
Levelfield Consultants, Singapore

Venue: Auditorium

Time: 17:45hr – 18:15hr

Accessibility Improves Quality of Life for All

Quality of life is often used to measure how good one feels about one's life. There are various factors that impact quality of life. These include economic, social and political environment, access to health care, education and employment, services and transportation, housing as well as recreation. Thus improving the accessibility of the built environment and transportation is the stepping stone that can significantly impact on the quality of life of everyone in society and to ensure their easy and safe interaction in the community they live in. Being able to go out to have dinner at the food court or restaurant, go shopping, watch a movie or go for a swim at the sports centre with family and friends who could have an impairment, disability or using an aid means that everyone in the group is reaping the benefits of being included. The Plenary will share how quality of life for everyone in the community such as pregnant mothers, parents with infants and young children, children, people lugging heavy luggage, those who are ill, injured or with an impairment, the old and not so old can be improved with accessibility and participation. While accessibility has improved over the years, more can still be done by countries to enhance accessibility for everyone in particular for people with disabilities and the elderly and thus improve their Quality of Life.

Workshop Sessions

Workshop 1: 24 Jul 2012 (Tue)

13:30hr–17:30hr @Lecture Theatre 1

Building Inclusive Communities

by University of Queensland (Australia) and LevelField
Consultants (Singapore)

Traditionally, disability has been understood as resulting from a health condition or impairment, with the focus being on personal deficits. More recently, the International Classification of Function, Disability and Health (ICF) (WHO, 2001) has described disability as being a consequence of the environment. Further, in defining health, the ICF moves away from attending to the impaired body structures and function to enabling people to engage equitably in activities and participate fully in society. Whilst much has been achieved in creating accessible environments, people with disabilities are at risk of remaining in the margins of society unless they are afforded the same rights and opportunities as their able bodied colleagues. This workshop will use a social model of disability to discuss the common barriers and facilitators to full participation. In particular, it will examine the ways in which the built environment, societal attitudes and policies, systems and services can be used to promote more inclusive communities.

Workshop 2: 24 July 2012 (Tue)

13:30hr – 17:30hr @Lecture Theatre 2

Mixed Reality Rehabilitation

by Industrial Research Limited (New Zealand)

Upper limb paralysis following stroke is a leading cause of disability and most rehabilitation is focused around compensation for the lost function. However, motor performance of adults with chronic stroke improves with repetitive, game-assisted, self-supported bilateral exercises. This presentation will overview learning and recovery that is possible as a result of plasticity of the brain. Various technologies will be discussed that can be used for virtual reality rehabilitation of the upper limb and a low cost system that an individual can use in their own home will be demonstrated.

Workshop 3: 25 July 2012 (Wed)
09:00hr -10:30hr @Room B03-13

Novel of Clinical Gait Analysis in Rehabilitation: Beyond the Naked Eyes

by King Chulalongkorn Memorial Hospital (Thailand)

Clinical gait analysis usually consists of 5 elements: videotape examination, measurement of general gait parameters, kinematics analysis, kinetic measurement, and electromyography (EMG). The human eye is simply not fast enough to capture and process all of the events that occur during an average gait cycle. Video recording of walking can providing a permanent record of the walk for subsequent analysis. Slow motion, freeze frame facilities and time coding can all enhance greatly the accuracy of observation. The ability to objectively quantify motion of clinical gait analysis is essential to our understanding of normal and abnormal movement patterns and the evaluation of rehabilitation treatment effectiveness. This workshop will focus on evidence-based medicine of what, when, why and how....for using clinical gait analysis. Cases demonstration and

discussion will be provided. Practical points of clinical gait analysis in rehabilitation medicine are highlight.

Workshop 4: 25 July 2012 (Wed)
09:00hr -10:30hr @Room B03-14

Accessing the iPhone: Introductory Strategies for the Visually Impaired

by National Institute of Education (Singapore)

This workshop seeks to introduce basic navigating skills for iPhone users with visual impairments. Learn about VoiceOver, Apple's built-in feature designed to make their devices more accessible to the blind and visually impaired. Be introduced to apps, especially useful to the visually impaired that are available for download. Participants will be given hands-on experience using this technology from the perspectives of blind users. To achieve maximum benefits from the workshop, participants are encouraged to bring their own iPad or iPhone along with your personal earpiece.

Workshop 5: 25 July 2012 (Wed)
09:00hr -10:30hr @ Room B03-15/16

The Gerontological Design Approach

by Temasek Polytechnic (Singapore)

The workshop is a taster of effective design thinking methods when designing for elderly. Gerontological Design focuses on providing effective solutions to improve the way of life for ageing individuals, through gerontological knowledge and design research methods to obtain better understanding of these individuals' preferences and requirements. Gerontological design also refers specifically to the study and practice of building design methods that support elderly users

in the built environment. The approach in Gerontological design is user-centric and works when it achieved aesthetic, function and usability effectiveness. In time, products and services relevant to the “silver industry” are expected to flood the marketplace. And with it, an increase in the demand for designers with a very good sense of the needs of an ageing population using the knowledge of gerontological design process.

Workshop 6: 25 July 2012 (Wed)
09:00hr -10:30hr @Room B03- 17

Multidisciplinary approach to prescribe Assistive Technology devices and measuring outcome of the device for Cerebral palsy clients and related physical disabilities

by The Spastic Children’s Association of Singapore
(Singapore)

The use of Assistive Technology (AT) devices is prevalent among cerebral palsy clients to maximize the opportunity for independent function and also to reduce the burden of care. However, the prescription of AT devices for CP is often a complicated process faced by OTs, PTs, and SLPs. Moreover, the use of AT devices is often funded by external sources, necessitating the need for effective outcome measurement. This workshop aims to provide participants with a brief overview of common AT devices used by cerebral palsy clients or by clients with related physical disabilities. In addition, the workshop seeks to demonstrate how a multidisciplinary process can be incorporated to justify, prioritize and recommend the best AT device for clients using a client centered approach when prescribing AT devices.

Workshop 7: 26 July 2012 (Thu)

11:00hr – 17:00hr @Room B03-15/16

Assistive Technology Fundamentals

by Nanyang Technological University (Singapore)
Singapore Polytechnic (Singapore)

This one day workshop is for clinicians (speech therapists, occupation therapists), AT Practitioners, education professionals, users and suppliers of varying level of knowledge of assistive technology. It will cover the basic principles and sciences of Assistive Technology, assessment of needs/goal identification, characteristics of technologies available to meet client needs, case studies and follow by an open discussion on the current issues on Assistive Technology.

Workshop 8: 26 July 2012 (Thu)

11:00 – 12:30hr @Room B03-14

Rehabilitation Games

by TTSH (Singapore)

Details not present during time of printing

Workshop 9: 26 July 2012 (Thu)

11:00hr -12:30hr @Room B03-17

State of the ART: Utilizing mainstream mobile technology for telecommunication and AAC

by LifeTec Queensland (Australia)

This presentation will cover accessibility options for mainstream mobile devices for both telecommunications as well as Alternative and Augmentative Communication applications available. The participants will be given an

overview of mainstream mobile platforms. Differences between available platforms will also be discussed. Solutions for voice control, direct access, mouse alternatives and switch access on different devices will be discussed and explored. Applications that can be used to enhance physical access will also be explored during the session. A range of Alternative and Augmentative Communication applications will also be discussed during the workshop. Limited amount of devices and applications may be available to participants to have hands on experiences depending on logistical factors.

Workshop 10: 26 July 2012 (Thu)
13:30hr -15:00hr @Room B03-13

**Establishment of Assistive Technology Services
Provisions in India: Needs and Challenges**
by Indian Spinal Injuries Centre, New Delhi (India)

Assistive Technology promotes greater independence by enabling people to perform tasks that they were formerly unable to accomplish, or had great difficulty accomplishing, by providing assistive technology devices and assistive technology services to accomplish such tasks. Assistive technology allows individuals with disabilities to function independently in community, education and employment activities. Assistive Technology Services are still not broadly into practice of Rehabilitation and similar professionals to provide required assistive devices and guidance at the Government-Public hospitals/rehabilitation centers/NGOs and other places. This workshop on Assistive Technology Services Establishment would make impact on the audiences and also provide them a unique opportunity to learn about the AT services and its provision toward improvement of Mobility, Accessibility and Transport.

Workshop 11: 26 July 2012 (Thu)
13:30hr – 17:00hr @Room B03-14

Upper limb robot-assisted rehabilitation and assessment
by Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
(ETH Zürich) (Switzerland),
Tan Tock Seng Hospital (Singapore)

Robotic devices are a promising solution to complement conventional therapy, and provide a unique platform for more objective and sensitive assessments, both of motor and sensory functions. Nevertheless, the use of robots for rehabilitation and assessment is still in its infancy, and many challenges remain on how to best take advantage of the unique features of robots, and translate these into significant benefits for a wide patient population. We will give an overview of how robots are currently used for rehabilitation and assessment, present outcomes of clinical studies using different robotic systems focusing on the upper limb, and discuss novel trends, including neuroscience robotics.

Workshop 12: 26 July 2012 (Thu)
13:30hr – 17:00hr @Room B03-17

**Assistive Technology and Occupational Therapy
Collaboration in the Classroom. A Model in California
Schools**
by OTChildren (USA)

In this presentation I will define the roles of Occupational Therapy and Assistive Technology in the California schools. Mandates from the State Department of Education, Credentialing Agencies and RESNA will provide a background for examination of current educational practices.

OTRs and AT Specialists ideally work together in the public school system, where areas of expertise overlap and complement each other. Examples and Case Studies from a school district in California will be used to illustrate how a student can benefit from a combined approach.

Forum Sessions

Forum 1: 25 July 2012 (Wed) 15:30hr – 17:00hr

Assistive & Rehabilitation Technology (ART) in an Inclusive Community

Panelists

Mr Chua Chin Kiat,

Chairman of Centre for Enabled Living, Singapore

Mrs Desleigh de Jonge

Associate Lecturer, University of Queensland, Australia

Mr Kevin Caves

Secretary, Executive Committee BOD for RESNA, USA

Mr Nekram Uphadyay,

Head, Department of Assistive Technology, Indian Spinal Injuries Centre, India.

Moderator:

Dr Bala S Rajaratnam, Nanyang Polytechnic, Singapore

Forum 2: 26 July 2012 (Thu) 13:30hr – 15:00hr

Assistive & Rehabilitation Technology (ART) is a business

Panelists

Mr R Raghunathan & Mr Murali Gangadharan,

PricewaterhouseCoopers, Singapore

Mr Lim Swee Tiam & Mr Steven Yap

Nanyang Polytechnic

Ms Low Pei Lin, Allen & Gledhill, Singapore

Thammasart University, Thailand

Moderator: Mr Dinesh Verma, V2U Healthcare Pte Ltd,

Singapore

Forum 3: 26 July 2012 (Thu) 15:30hr – 17:00hr

ART Inventor Experience

Panelists

Mr Marcus King, Research Leader Industrial Research Ltd, New Zealand

Ms Esther Wang, Designer (Rabbit Ray), Singapore

Ms Wantanee Phantachat, National Electronic and Computer Technology Center (NECTEC), Thailand

Moderator: Dr Bala S Rajaratnam, Nanyang Polytechnic,

Singapore

i-CREATe 2012 Program Overview
(ITE College East, Singapore)

Day ONE - 24 July 2012 (Tue)

0800 - 1500			
Registration @ Level 3 (Admin Block - Foyer)			
Time	Function Hall	Room B03-15/16	Lecture Theatre 1
0900 - 1230	Poster exhibit set up & Student Design Challenge move in		
1230 - 1330	Lunch		
1330 - 1500	SDC Presentations (Design)	SDC Presentations (Technology)	WORKSHOP 1: Building Inclusive Communities by
1500 - 1530	Tea Break		
1530 - 1730	SDC Presentations (Design)	SDC Presentations (Technology)	University of Queensland (AU) Levelfield Consultants (SG)

0800 - 1500		
Registration @ Level 3 (Admin Block - Foyer)		
Time	Lecture Theatre 2	Off-site
0900 - 1230		(Site Visit A) ITE College East & Society for the Physically Disabled (Site Visit B) Spastic Children Association of Singapore & Centre for Advanced Rehabilitation Therapeutics (CART) @ TTSH
1230 - 1330	Lunch	
1330 - 1500	WORKSHOP 2: Mixed Reality Rehabilitation by	
1500 - 1530	Tea Break	
1530 - 1730	Industrial Research Limited (NZ) & St Luke's Hospital (SG)	

Day TWO - 25 July 2012 (Wed)

Registration @ Level 3 (Admin Block - Foyer)			
Time	Function Hall	Auditorium	Room B03-13
0800 - 1500			
0900 - 1030	Students Design Challenge Prototype Judging		WORKSHOP 3: Novel of Clinical Gait Analysis in Rehabilitation by Chulalongkorn University (TH)
1030 - 1100			Tea Break
1100 - 1230			Paper Presentations P1 Rehabilitation Technology
1230 - 1330	Lunch		
1330 - 1500	Posters Exhibit & SDC Open to All		Plenary Speaker 1 : Dr Roger Gassart (CH) ***** Plenary Speaker 2 : Mr Marcus King (NZ)
1500 - 1530			Tea Break
1530 - 1700			FORUM 1: Assistive & Rehabilitation Technology (ART) in an Inclusive Community
1700 - 1815			Plenary Speaker 3 : Mrs Desleigh de Jonge (AU) ***** Plenary Speaker 4 : Ms Judy Wee (SG)
1815 - 1830			SDC Award Presentation
1900 - 2100			Dinner @ ITE Atrium "hawker fare nite" * for FULL pass delegates & all SDC students

Registration @ Level 3 (Admin Block - Foyer)			
Time	Room B03-14	Room B03-15/16	Room B03-17
0800 - 1500			
0900 - 1030	WORKSHOP 4: Accessing the iphone for Visually Impaired by National Institute of Education (SG)	WORKSHOP 5: The Gerontological Design Approach by Temasek Polytechnic (SG)	WORKSHOP 6: Multipledisciplinary Approach to Prescribe AT devices for Cerebral Palsy Clients by Spastic Children Association of S'pore (SG)
1030 - 1100	Tea Break		
1100 - 1230	Paper Presentations P2 Assistive Technology	Paper Presentations P3 Augmentative & Alternative Communication & Inclusive Community	Paper Presentations P4 Special Education
1230 - 1330	Lunch		
1330 - 1500			
1500 - 1530			
1530 - 1700			
1700 - 1815			
1815 - 1830			
1900 - 2100			

Day THREE - 26 July 2012 (Thu)

Registration @ Level 3 (Admin Block - Foyer)			
Time	Function Hall	Room B03-13	Room B03-14
0900 - 1030	Posters Exhibit & Student Design Challenge Open to All	Paper Presentations P5 Rehabilitation Studies	Paper Presentations P6; NeuroRehabilitation
1030 - 1100		Tea Break	
1100 - 1230		Paper Presentations P8 Biomechanics & Biotech	WORKSHOP 8: Rehabilitation Games Tan Tock Seng Hospital (SG)
1230 - 1330		Lunch	
1330 - 1500	FORUM 2 ART Development is a business	WORKSHOP 10: Establishment of AT Services in India by Indian Spinal Injuries Centre (IN)	WORKSHOP 11: Upper limb robot-assisted rehabilitation and assessment
1500 - 1530	Tea Break		
1530 - 1700	FORUM 3 ART Inventor Experience		by ETHZ (CH) & TTSH (SG)

Time	Room B03-15/16	Room B03-17
0900 - 1030	WORKSHOP 7: Assistive Technology Fundamentals	Paper Presentations P7 Assistive & Rehabilitation Technology (ART) for Aging
1030 - 1100	Tea Break	
1100 - 1230	by Nanyang Technological University (SG)	WORKSHOP 9 State of the ART : Utilizing mainstream mobile technology for telecommunications & AAC by LifeTec (AU)
1230 - 1330	Lunch	
1330 - 1500	& Singapore Polytechnic (SG)	WORKSHOP 12: AT & OT Collaboration in Classroom. A model in California Schools
1500 - 1530	Tea Break	
1530 - 1700		by OTChildren (US)

updated on 10 July 2012

* Please note that this is a tentative program and is subject to changes.

Paper Presentations (Day 2 – 25 July 2012)

P1 – Rehabilitation Technology

11:00hr – 12:30 hr @ Room B03-13

P1-1 11:00-11:15	An Augmented Reality Based Virtual Keyboards for Assistive Technology Soh Khim ONG, Xin WANG, A.Y.C NEE National University of Singapore, Singapore
P1-2 11:15-11:30	Tracking Daily Activity using Smart Phones Jatuporn CHINRUNGRUENG, Seksun SARTSATIT National Electronics and Computer Technology Center, Thailand
P1-3 11:30-11:45	Master-Slave control for walking rehabilitation robot Nakrob WANICHNUKHROX, Thavida MANEEWARN, Szathys SONGSCHON King Mongkut's University of Technology Thonburi, Thailand
P1-4 11:45-12:00	Semi Portable Rehabilitation System for Upper Limb Disability The-Kiet LU, Edwin FOO, Bala S RAJARATNAM, I KANNAPPAN Nanyang Polytechnic, Singapore
P1-5 12:00-12:15	WEFRE Rehab System Winai CHONNAPARAMUTT, Eakkaluk CHANTHABUDSRI, Worakarn RUNGKAO, Wissarut SAPSRI National Electronics and Computer Technology Center, Thailand

P1-6 12:15-12:30	Development of a Surface Electromyography Biofeedback Unit for the Rehabilitation of Upper Limb Yan Ling Cynthia SIM, Weilin MENG, Boon Wee William TAN ITE College West, Singapore
Poster Presentations	
Po1-1 12:30-12:32	Kinect Based Tele-Rehabilitation Bingbing NI, Yong PEI, Stefan WINKLER Advanced Digital Science Center, Singapore
Po1-2 12:32-12:34	Combining VR and dance movement therapy for children with Cerebral Palsy Michelle NG, Bala S RAJARATNAM, D Senthil KUMAR Nanyang Polytechnic, Thailand

P2 – Assistive Technology

11:00-12:30hr @ Room B03-14

P2-1 11:00-11:15	A Wearable Navigation System for Low Vision Users Jie ZHANG, Mengyu ZHAO, Soh Khim ONG, Andrew Yeh-Ching NEE National University of Singapore, Singapore
P2-2 11:15-11:30	A Novel Design of OTP-based Authentication Scheme Using Smart phones and 2-D Barcodes for the Visually Impaired Longhua LI Prince of Songkla University, Thailand

ChulaDAISY: An Automated DAISY Audio Book Generation
 P2-3 Proadpran PUNYABUKKANA, Nat
 LERTWONGKHANAKOOL,
 11:30- Natthawut KERTKEIDKACHORN, Surapol
 11:45 VORAPATRATOM,
 Pawamrat HIRANKAN, Atiwong SUCHATO
 Chulalongkorn University, Thailand

Chula-FungPloen: Assistive Software for Listening to Online Contents
 P2-4 Atiwong SUCHATO, Varayut
 LERDKANLAYANAWAT,
 11:45- Surada LERKPATOMSAK, Proadpran
 12:00 PUNYABUKKANA
 Atiwong SUCHATO
 Chulalongkorn University, Thailand

Design and Implementation of a communication protocol for Knee Assistive Device with Distributed Control System
 P2-5 Tomasz M LUBECKI, Chee-Meng CHEW, Chee
 12:00- Leong TEO,
 12:15 Sean Efreem SABASTIAN
 National University of Singapore, Singapore

A New Web Interface for the Visually Impaired to Access Facebook
 P2-6 Kamonwan PAKDEECHOTE, Pichaya TANDAYYA
 12:15- Prince of Songkla University, Thailand
 12:30

Poster Presentations

Po2-1 **Mechanical efficiency of lever propulsion in manual wheelchair locomotion**
 12:30- Jordon LUI, Jeswin JEYASURYA, William SHEEL,
 12:32 Mahsa SADEGHI, Bonita SAWATZKY
 University of British Columbia, Canada

Po2-2 **A Comparative Study on International Standards of Assistive Listening Devices**
 12:32- Eun-Jeong CHO, Chan-Hoi HUR, Ji-Hye KIM, Shin-
 12:34 Jung KANG, Hyeon-Joo OH
 National Institute of Food and Drug Safety Evaluation, Korea

**P3 – Augmentative & Alternative Communication & Inclusive Community,
 11:00-12:30hr @Room B03-15/16**

P3-1 **Association Strategies of a Symbol Sequence for Producing Thai Words Used in Thai Picture-Based Communication System**
 Sarinya CHOMPOOBUTR, , Wantanee
 11:00- PHANTACHAT, Puttachart POTIBAL
 11:15 National Electronics and Computer Technology Center (NECTEC), Thailand

P3-2 **Icon Combination for Thai Picture-Based Communication system**
 *Puttachart POTIBAL, **Sarinya CHOMPOOBUTR,
 11:15- **Wantanee PHANTACHAT, **Monthika BORIBOON
 11:30 *Kasetsart University, Thailand
 **Thailand, National Electronics and Computer Technology Center (NECTEC), Thailand

P3-3 11:30-11:45	Problems and some solutions for the temporally dwellings built after the disasters *Jiro SAGARA, **Etsumi OKIGAWA, ***Tamotsu IMURA, ****Taizo YOSHIDA *Kobe Design University, **Kanagawa Rehab Center, ***Chubu Gakuin University, ****Tohoku Bunka Gakuen College, Japan
P3-4 11:45-12:00	Universal design for social inclusion: Entertainment an interpersonal Communication. Sami BEN FRADJ Kobe Design University, Japan
P3-5 12:00-12:15	Avoiding the Digital Divide: Rethinking ICT Inclusion in Singapore Meng Ee WONG National Institute of Education, Singapore
P3-6 12:15-12:30	Towards an inclusive Singapore: The Accessibility Master Plan Siam Imm GOH, Adeline LOO Building & Construction Authority, Singapore
Poster Presentations	
Po3-1 12:30-12:32	Street Directory and Barrier-free Routing for Wheelchair Users Waiming KONG, Tsu Soo TAN, Zin Ko Ko MIN, Fung Yuean LUNG, Teck Kim LEE, *Hwee Lin TAY. Nanyang Polytechnic, Singapore. *Society for the Physically Disabled, Singapore

**P4 –Special Education
11:00hr – 12:30hr @Room B03-17**

P4-1 11:00-11:15	Triangulation of psychopomp, bot and avatar to integrate psychogogy and technology as a learning activity system design for autism treatment Noel Kok Hwee CHIA, Norman Kiak Nam KEE, Yiyu CAI, National Institute of Education, Singapore
P4-2 11:15-11:30	Universal Design for Learning (UDL1) and Living (UDL2) in Virtual Reality-based Treatments for Children with Autism Norman Kiak Nam KEE, Noel Kok Hwee CHIA, Yiyu CAI National Institute of Education, Singapore
P4-3 11:30-11:45	Task Facilitator for Special Education using MIRA Bama SIRINIVASAN, Ranjani PARTHASARATHI Anna University, India
P4-4 11:45-12:00	The Literacy of Integrating Assistive Technology into Classroom Instruction for Special Education Teachers in Taiwan Chi Nung CHU, Ming Chung CHEN, Chien-Chuan KO China University of Technology, Taiwan
P4-5 12:00-12:15	Harnessing iPad for Lesson Study within the Triple-D Framework in Special Education Noel Kok Hwee CHIA, Norman Kiak Nam KEE, National Institute of Education, Singapore

P4-6 12:15- 12:30	Robotic Technology for Teaching Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder: A Feasibility Study *Kimberlee JORDAN, *Marcus KING, **Sophia HELLERSTETH, Anna WIREN, Hilda MILLIGAN *Industrial Research Ltd, New Zealand, **Umea University, Sweden
Poster Presentations	
Po4-1 12:30- 12:32	Assistive technology and children with learning disabilities. Partimokkh PROMCHUAY, Todsapol NGANPAIROJ, Akkarat YAMSEANG Samitivaj Hospital, Thailand
Po4-2 12:32- 12:34	A Design of Adaptive Error Feedback Ear-Training System for Learners with Learning Difficulty *Yu Ting HUANG, **Chi Nung CHU *Shih Chien University, Taiwan. **China University of Technology, Taiwan

Paper Presentations (Day 3 – 26 July 2012)

P5 - Rehabilitation Studies **09:00hr – 10:30hr @Room B03-13**

P5-1 09:00- 09:15	Feasibility Study on Applying the Quadratic Filter for ECG R-Peak Detection Preprocessing Saranya CHAIWISOOD, Pornchai PHUKPATTARANONT, Booncharoen WONGKITTISUKSA Prince of Songkla University, Thailand
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P5-2 09:15- 09:30	Optimal intra-dialytic exercise protocol for improving the toxin removal in hemodialysis patients Yasmin AHMAD, Vaibhav MAHESHWARI, Gade Pandu RANGAIAH, Titus LAU, Lakshminarayanan SAMAVEDHAM. National University of Singapore, Singapore
P5-3 09:30- 09:45	Improving Reminiscence Therapy through Active Brainwave Analysis Choong Wu Gary LIM Nanyang Polytechnic, Singapore
P5-4 09:45- 10:00	Investigation of Facial Infrared Thermography during interaction with Therapeutic Pet Robot during Cognitive training: A quantitative approach *Jaichandar KS, *Mohan Rajesh ELARA, **Edgar A Martinez GARCIA *Singapore Polytechnic, Singapore **Universidad Autonoma de Ciudad Juarez, Mexico
Po5-1 10:00- 10:02	Poster Presentations A Proof of Concept Study to Develop System for Upper Limb Rehabilitation at Home Zhiqiang LUO, Nam Beng TAN Nanyang Polytechnic, Singapore
Po5-2 10:02- 10:04	Accuracy Of Tele-video To Access Physical Function ^{1,2} Helen HOENIG, ³ Latoya TATE, ³ Sarina DUMBLETON, ^{1,2} Christy CONE, ^{1,2} Michelle MORGAN, ² Lawrence R. LANDERMAN, ² Kevin CAVES ¹ Durham Veterans Administration Medical Center, ² Duke University Medical Center, ³ Duke University Physical School, USA

Po5-3 10:04- 10:06	Synchronization between cardiac and locomotor rhythms increase stroke volume during human walking Shinta TAKEUCHI, Yusuke NISHIDA, Takashi MIZUSHIMA Hamamatsu University School of Medicine, University Hospital, Japan
Po5-4 10:06- 10:08	A Statistical Method of detecting EMG threshold for assistive device applications. J.HONG, Korea University
Po5-5 10:08- 10:10	Control of the Body's Center of Mass Motion Relative to the Center of Pressure in Patients with Parkinson's Disease During Obstacle Crossing Tung-Wu LU, Zhi-You CHEN, Ruey-Meei WU National University of Taiwan, Taiwan
Po5-6 10:10- 10:12	Changes of Foot Contact Patterns when Walking onto Moving Surfaces of Different Speed in Young Adults Wei-Chun HSU, Tung-Wu LU National Taiwan University

**P6 - NeuroRehabilitation,
09:00hr – 10:30hr @ Room B03-14**

P6-1 09:00- 09:15	Ankle-Foot Passive Motion Prototype for Stroke Patients Nida VONGSAVAT, Kittichai THARAWADEEPIMUK, Yodchanan WONGSAWAT, Benjaporn SAKSIRI Mahidol University, Thailand
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P6-2 09:15- 09:30	Development of upper and lower extremity rehabilitation device for brain computer interface Kittichai THARAWADEEPIMUK, Panya KAIMUK, Yodchanan WONGSAWAT, Mahidol university, Thailand .
P6-3 09:30- 09:45	Facilitating Early Onset of Therapy after Stroke: An Arm Glove Design for Self-Regulation of Muscle Activation Subhasis BANERJI, John HENG, Barry PEREIRA National University of Singapore, Singapore
P6-4 09:45- 10:00	Upper Extremity Rehabilitation after Stroke: Biofeedback Gaming for Attention and Muscle Use Subhasis BANERJI, John HENG, Barry PEREIRA National University of Singapore, Singapore
P6-5 10:15- 10:30	Wii-Habilitation in Stroke Patients: A Systematic Review Mullika SANTAYAYON, Jagkapong PIPITPUKDEE, Wantanee PHANTACHAT National Electronics and Computer Technology Center, Thailand
P6-6 10:30- 10:45	Can Virtual Reality integrated within conventional rehabilitation enhance balance recovery after stroke? Zhilong Jerome-Christian NG, B.S. RAJARATNAM, Tian Ma Tim XU Nanyang Polytechnic, Singapore

	Poster Presentations
Po6-1 10:45-10:47	Bayesian Methods for Improving P300 Speller Performance Chandra S THROCKMORTON, Kenneth COLWELL, **David B RYAN, **Eric SELLERS, Leslie COLLINS, *Kevin CAVES Duke University, *Duke Medical Center **East Tennessee State University
Po6-2 10:47-10:49	The effects of including Virtual Reality into rehabilitation of trunk control of patients after stroke. Bala S RAJARATNAM, Kai En Jasmine GUI, Jia Lin Kellyn LEE Nanyang Polytechnic

P7 – Assistive Rehabilitation Technology for Aging
09:00hr -10:30hr @ Room B03-17

P7-1 09:00-09:15	LifeVision: Integrating Heart Rate Sensing in Lifelogging Camera for Accurate Risk Diagnosis for the Elderly *Mohan Rajesh ELARA MOHAN, Hyowon LEE, **Jaichandar KS, Carlos Acosta Antonio CALDERON. *Singapore University of Technology and Design, Singapore **Singapore Polytechnic, Singapore
P7-2 09:15-09:30	A Responsive Home Environment for the Elderly Andrew YEW, Jie ZHANG, Soh Khim ONG, Andrew NEE National University of Singapore, Singapore

P7-3 09:30-09:45	Tangible Social-Media Application for the Elderly *Jeffery WU, **Chee Koon LIM *Gerontological Designer, Singapore **Temasek Polytechnic, Singapore
P7-4 09:45-10:00	Mobile Assistant for Elderly (MAE) Thet SWE, Cheah Huei YOONG, Zheng Xian LEE, Shou Yee NEO Ngee Ann Polytechnic, Singapore
	Poster Presentations
Po7-1 10:00-10:02	Slight ingenious methods of improving environment of elderly people with dementia *Chiho OSHIMA, Hikaru SHIMOGAKI *Waseda University, College of Social Work
Po7-2 10:02-10:04	Setting-Up Physical Fitness Analysis Platform In Older Adults With The Technique of Cloud Computing: A Pilot Study in Rehabilitation Center of New Taipei City *Tsung-Ching LIN, **Sung WANG, *** Tzyy-Yuan SHAIING, Chao-Chi HONG *Far Eastern Hospital, **Oriental Institute of Technology, ***National Taiwan Normal University
Po7-3 10:04-10:06	The Screening of Sarcopenia By Bioelectrical Impedance Analysis At Rehabilitation Clinic In Taiwan Medical Center *Tsung-Ching LIN, *Min-Fang HSU, **Chao-Chi HONG, ***Hsiu-Ling CHOU *Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, **Oriental Institute of Technology, ***Taipei Veteran Hospital.

Po7-4 10:06- 10:08	Effects of long-term Tai Chi Chuan on the inter-joint coordination of the lower limbs during obstacle-crossing in the elderly. *TW LU, * SC CHEN,** TJ HO, JG LIN *National Taiwan University, **Medical University Beigang Hospital, Taiwan ***China Medical University, Taiwan
Po7-5 10:08- 10:10	Effects of Tai-Chin Chuan on the control of body's center of mass motion during obstacle crossing in the elderly. *TJ HO, ** SC CHEN, **TW LU,*** JG LIN *Medical University Beigang Hospital, Taiwan **National Taiwan University, Taiwan, ***China Medical University, Taiwan
Po7-6 10:10- 10:12	Virtual Dementia Home Series: Bathroom-Toilet Wan-Koo May YEOK, Chin Hong TAN, Joan LEE Nanyang Polytechnic

P8 –Biomechanics & Biotech

11:00hr - 1230 hr @ Room B03-13

P8-1 11:00- 11:15	Comparison of variables of heart rate variability in distinguishing between severities of depression *Wen-Dien CHANG, Ping-Tung LAI, Chien-Tsung TSAI *China Medical University, Taiwan **Da-Chien General Hospital, Taiwan
P8-2 11:15- 11:30	Designing for patient-centred factors in medical adherence technology Aisyah HAMID, Pin Sym FOONG National University of Singapore, Singapore

P8-3 11:30- 11:45	Quantification of diaphragm muscle thickness using ultrasound imaging: A Preliminary study Nor Najwatul Akmal Ab RAHMAN, Devinder Kaur Ajit SINGH, Norhafidzah Mohamed SHARIF, Radhika SRIDHARAN, Raymond LEE, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Malaysia
P8-4 11:45- 12:00	Effect of Sitting Posture on Spine Joint Angles and Forces Mengjie HUANG, Ian GIBSON, Taeyong LEE, Khatereh HAJIZADEH National University of Singapore, Singapore
P8-5 12:00- 12:15	Development of a Virtual Musculo-Skeletal, Multi-Body Scoliotic Spine Model Khatereh HAJIZADEH, Ian GIBSON, Gabriel LIU, Mengjie HUANG National University of Singapore, Singapore
P8-6 12:15- 12:30	A novel optical method of guiding epidural catheter placement for epidural block Yin CHANG, Chien-Kun TING National Yang-Ming University, Taiwan
Po8-1 12:30- 12:32	Poster Presentations Biomechanical analysis of different thoracolumbar orthosis designs for conservative management of kyphosis YH KIM, C JUN, DY JUNG, SJ LEE Inje university

Student Design Challenge 2012

The Student Design Challenge 2012 is into the 5th installment. The SDC encourages students to find creative and innovative solutions to improve the quality of living of elderly and people with disability. For this year, there will be two categories for the challenge:

Design Category

Students are expected to apply User-Centered Design process to produce a concept that makes life easier for its users. Their solution could use any type of technology and result in an improvement to the quality of life, 'make life easier' for its users or enhance the user experience of the solution.

Technology Category

Student entries are expected to apply principles in engineering and information technology principles to design and implement Assistive & Rehabilitative Technology solution to address the issues/problems faced by the needy, their caregiver and clinicians.

The theme for Student Design Challenge 2012 will be ***'Assistive & Rehabilitation Technology in an Inclusive Community'***

Presentation

All teams are required to do an oral presentation covering the key ideas of the project. The presentations are scheduled at 13:30hr-17:30hr on 24 July 2012, Design teams will be presenting at the Function Hall and the Technology teams will be presenting at room B03-15/16. Each presentation is 5 minutes.

Poster & Prototype Display

All teams are required to display their poster and prototype at the Student Design Challenge Exhibition Area, from 24 July 2012, 08:30hr to 26 July 2012, 17:00hr At least one team member must be present at their booth during the above session.

Awards

Champion	Trophy, USD1,400 & certificate for all members
1st Runner-up	Trophy & USD700& certificate for all members
2nd Runner-up	Trophy, USD350 & certificate for all members
Merit award	Trophy & certificate for all members

- Peer's choice award certificate for all members. The award is to be decided by the SDC participants. Each team is allowed to cast one vote on the most deserving team entry but cannot vote for their own team. The votes have to be casted at the end of the presentation session.
- Public's choice award- certificate for all members. The award is to be decided by the public visiting the exhibition. Upon registering for the exhibition, each visitor will be given a voting sheet where they have to complete and drop into the voting box at the registration booth after visiting the SDC booths.
- Best presentation award- certificate for all members. The award will be decided by the panel of judges based on the presentation part of the judging criteria.

- Best poster award- certificate for all members. The award will be decided by the panel of judges based on the poster part of the judging criteria.
- Best prototype award- certificate for all members. The award will be decided by the panel of judges based on the prototype part of the judging criteria.

Authors Index

AHMAD Yasmin	P5-2
BANERJI Subhasis	P6-3
	P6-4
BEN FRADJ Sami	P3-4
BORIBOON Monthika	P3-2
CAI Yiyu	P4-1
	P4-2
CALDERON Carlos Acosta A	P7-1
CHAIWISOOD Saranya	P5-1
CHANG Wen-Dien	P8-1
CHANG Yin	P8-6
CHANTHABUDSR Eakkaluk	P1-5
CHEN Ming Chung	P4-4
CHEW Chee Meng	P2-5
CHIA Kok Hwee Noel	P4-1
	P4-2
	P4-5
CHINRUNGRUENG Jatuporn	P1-2
CHOMPOOBUTR Sarinya	P3-1
	P3-2
CHONNAPARAMUTT Winai	P1-5
CHU Chi Nung	P4-4
ELARA Mohan Rajesh	P5-4
	P7-1

FOO Edwin	P1-4	KS Jaichandar	P5-4
FOONG Pin Sym	P8-2		P7-1
GARCIA Edgar A Martinez	P5-4	LAI Ping-Tung	P8-1
GIBSON Ian	P8-4	LAU Titus	P5-2
	P8-5	LEE Hyowon	P7-1
GOH Siam Imm	P3-6	LEE Raymond	P8-3
HAJIZADEH Khaterreh	P8-4	LEE Zhen Xian	P7-4
	P8-5	LEE Taeyong	P8-4
HAMID Aisyah	P8-2	LERDKANLAYANAWAT Varayut	P2-4
HELLERSTETH Sophia	P4-6	LERPATOMSAK Surada	P2-4
HENG John	P6-3	LERTWONGKHANAKOOL Nat	P2-3
	P6-4	LI Longhua	P2-2
HIRANKAN Pawamrat	P2-3	LIM Chee Koon	P7-3
HUANG Mengjie	P8-4	LIM Choong Wu Gary	P5-3
	P8-5	LIU Gabriel	P8-5
IMURA Tamotsu	P3-3	LOO Adeline	P3-6
JORDAN Kimberlee	P4-6	LU The-Kiet	P1-4
KAIMUK Panya	P6-2	LUBECKI Tomasz M	P2-5
KANNAPPAN I	P1-4	MAHESHWARI Vaibhav	P5-2
KEE Kiak Nam Norman	P4-1	MANEEWARN Thavida	P1-3
	P4-2	MENG Weilin	P1-6
	P4-5	MILLIGAN Hilda	P4-6
KERTKEIDKACHORN Natthawut	P2-3	NEE Yeh-Ching Andrew	P1-1
KING Marcus	P4-6		P2-1
KO Chien Chuan	P4-4		P7-2

NEO Shou Yee	P7-4	SAGARA Jiro	P3-3
NG Zhilong Jerome C	P6-6	SAKSIRI Benjaporn	P6-1
OKIGAWA Etsumi	P3-3	SAMAVEDHAM Lakshminarayanan	P5-2
ONG Soh Khim	P1-1	SANTAYAYON Mullika	P6-5
	P2-1	SAPSRI Wissarut	P1-5
	P7-2	SARTSATIT Seksun	P1-2
PAKDEECHOTE Kamonwan	P2-6	SHARIF Norhafidzah Mohamed	P8-3
PARTHASARATHI Ranjani	P4-3	SIM Yan Ling Cynthia	P1-6
PEREIRA Barry	P6-3	SINGH Devinder Kaur Ajit	P8-3
	P6-4	SIRINIVASAN Bama	P4-3
PHANTACHAT Wantanee	P3-1	SONGSCHON Szathys	P1-3
	P3-2	SRIDHARAN Radhika	P8-3
	P6-5	SUCHATO Atiwong	P2-4
PHUKPATTARANONT Pornchai	P5-1		P2-3
PIPITPUKDEE Jagkapong	P6-5	SWE Thet	P7-4
POTIBAL Puttachart	P3-1	TAN Boon Wee William	P1-6
	P3-2	TANDAYYA Pichaya	P2-6
PUNYABUKKANA Proadpran	P2-3	TEO Chee Leong	P2-5
	P2-4	THARAWADEEPIMUK Kittichai	P6-1
RAHMAN Nor Najwatul Akmal Ab	P8-3		P6-2
RAJARATNAM Bala S	P1-4	TING Chien-kun	P8-6
	P6-6	TSAI Chien-Tsung	P8-1
RANGAIAH Gade Pandu	P5-2	VONGSAVAT Nida	P6-1
RUNGKAO Worakarn	P1-5	VORAPATRATOM Surapol	P2-3
SABASTIAN Sean Efrem	P2-5	WANG Xin	P1-1

WANICHNUKHROX Nakrob	P1-3
WIREN Anna	P4-6
WONG MengEe	P3-5
WONGKITTISUKSA Booncharoen	P5-1
WONGSAWAT Yodchanan	P6-1
	P6-2
WU Jeffrey	P7-3
XU Tian Ma Tim	P6-6
YEW Andrew	P7-2
YOONG Cheah Huei	P7-4
ZHANG Jie	P2-1
	P7-2
ZHAO Mengyu	P2-1

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